

TRAINING OF TEACHERS IN THE CONDITIONS OF SOCIAL COOPERATION IN A HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION

Umarov Alisher Yusubjanovich

Vice-rector of the Academy of Public Administration under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Doctor of pedagogical sciences, professor

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Abstract. *This article talks about the integrative mechanisms of training pedagogues in the conditions of social cooperation in higher education institutions.*

Keywords: *Higher educational institution, social cooperation, pedagogue, integrative mechanisms, education and upbringing, pedagogical strategy, pedagogical activity, psychological-pedagogical mechanisms, integrated educational institutions, results, development of the educational process.*

Social cooperation in the pedagogical activity of an educational institution is characterized by the emergence and formation of new forms, connections, obtained effects and results. Researchers describe this phenomenon based on the specific characteristics of professional education. Social cooperation in the educational system is based on attracting additional resources for the development of the educational process of the institution. If we consider the peculiarities of establishing cooperative relations with preschool education, public education and professional education, public representatives, then we can identify the main aspect characteristic of these relations.

Social cooperation in higher education institutions can be implemented at several levels:

- 1) within the higher education system itself - between different social groups of this professional community or separate educational institutions;
- 2) within the framework of the interaction of the employees of the higher education system with representatives of other professional groups;
- 3) in the system of higher professional education as a special field of social life that makes a certain contribution to the formation of civil society.

Social cooperation arises from the needs and requirements of the higher pedagogical education system and includes social-labor relations in the field of education, relations between teachers and students, the parent community and teaching staff, education the relationship between the institution and the board of trustees, and they require the creation of university complexes and other educational structures. The third level allows to change, design, approve and establish new socially significant functions of the system of higher professional education in the society in order to implement the state order for the training of specialists. According to Ye. V. Bondarevskaya, the implementation of such a social order requires a fundamental change in the current pedagogical education system.

In the process of training pedagogues in higher education institutions, the implementation of mutual activities of educational subjects in internal and external cooperation is the technological basis of ensuring the external and internal aspects of training future pedagogues for the profession on the basis of social cooperation.

We will consider the definition and its content to reveal the essence of social cooperation in the modern changing conditions of education using the methods of analysis, synthesis and

classification.

There are many scientific views on socialization and social cooperation, for example:

Socialization is used to define a two-way process. On the one hand, the formation of a person in interaction with the environment, the state, social society, nature and the institutional structures of the social environment, as a result of which a person is formed by the means of teaching, training and education and will be formed in relation to this time acquires (in whole or in part) the system of knowledge, values, norms, instructions and reasons related to society and groups. On the one hand, it is the process of acquiring social culture through the means of entering a certain social environment, the system of social relations. On the other hand, it is the process of identifying oneself as a person by influencing life situations and surrounding people.

Social cooperation is understood by I.M. Remorenko as "joint collective distributive activity of various social groups, which leads to positive and sharing by all participants of this activity." There are three main forms of the phenomenon of social cooperation, in which it is distinguished as an interaction of social subjects, a social movement, and a social cultural phenomenon. As a module of this phenomenon, the subject-object social movement, based on the scientific work of S.A. Ivanov, distinguishes four basic elements:

- subject of action (person, social group)
- object of action ("thinking and behavior of social partners:
 - interprets as their adjustment, interests, value and norms);
 - the process of social action
 - situational conditions.

It is also necessary to determine the main principles of social cooperation. I.A. Leviskaya writes in the article about social cooperation: "The main principles of social cooperation include the following:

- respect and take into account the interests of the contracting parties;
- the interest of the contracting parties in participating in contractual relations;
- equal rights and trust of parties entering into social cooperation relations;
- freedom of choice and discussion of issues within the scope of social cooperation;
- voluntary acceptance of obligations of social partners based on mutual agreements;
- systematicity in conducting negotiations and consultations on issues within the scope of social cooperation;
- social partners and their representatives have certain powers during negotiations and signing the cooperation agreement;
- the validity of the provision of obligations accepted by partners, that is, the object of the agreement on cooperation should be activities provided only with their own funds and resources;
- obligation to execute the agreements reached;
- systematic control of the implementation of the agreements, contracts and decisions adopted within the framework of social cooperation by each of the parties signing the agreement".

The main components, principles, modules of the system of social cooperation, bilateral opportunities and functions-mechanisms by the subjects of cooperative relations ultimately lead to the determination of a certain type or combination of social cooperation. The development of social cooperation in the education of students is carried out in various forms, the school and the social partner create mutually beneficial conditions for each other. The effectiveness of teacher training is closely related to the mechanisms of its implementation.

In modern higher education institutions, the goal of their educational and training activities is to use complex methods of solving large-scale professional issues in various, at the same time rapidly changing conditions, with certain personal qualities. is becoming the preparation of graduates with high efficiency in achieving target tasks. There is no doubt that there is a possibility to achieve this goal, but since it is complicated by a number of socio-economic factors, it is equally necessary to develop not only a pedagogical strategy for achieving the goal, but also to study in detail the means of its implementation. In this situation, the concept of pedagogical strategy implies complex tasks that ensure proportional results, as well as means of making changes to tasks for a certain period of time and a system of monitoring their execution. The methods and ways of controlling the execution of strategic tasks are the mechanism of strategy implementation.

All mechanisms for implementing the pedagogical strategy of forming the competitiveness of a graduate of a higher education institution can be classified on the following basis:

- scope of implementation - at the level of the student (as a subject of the pedagogical process), at the level of the department (faculty), at the level of the higher education institution. For example, we can talk about psychological mechanisms at the student level, organizational-management mechanisms at the department (faculty) level, and socio-economic mechanisms at the level of the higher education institution - about the implementation of the pedagogical strategy for the formation of a competitive graduate of the higher education institution.

- validity periods - short-term, medium-long-term and long-term. For example, the mechanisms for implementing the pedagogical strategy of short-term actions can include innovative, informational and other directions that have a short "shelf life" and must be constantly changed depending on many factors of the process of forming a competitive graduate-student. . In turn, the mechanism of organizational and methodical directions in some sense ensures the integrity of the entire process of forming the competitiveness of the graduate, and they are set for a long period;

- number of subjects - individually, collectively and as a group. For example, if the psychological-pedagogical mechanisms of the implementation of the pedagogical strategy for the formation of a competitive graduate of the higher educational institution are individually oriented, the scientific-methodical or information-pedagogical mechanisms are oriented to the team. Legal and socio-economic mechanisms, in turn, belong to group mechanisms according to the number of subjects.

The presented classification reflects the secondary characteristics of the mechanisms of implementation of the pedagogical strategy of forming a graduate of a competitive higher education institution. As a primary basis for this classification, in our opinion, it is necessary to consider their common directed vector.

Therefore, we recommend using the following classification of mechanisms for implementing the pedagogical strategy of forming the competitiveness of a graduate of a higher education institution:

- psychological and pedagogical;
- organizational management;
- scientific and methodical;
- socio-economic;
- information-pedagogical;
- related to personnel;

- legal.

Below, we will consider the essence and content of the mechanisms for implementing the pedagogical strategy of forming the competitiveness of graduates of higher educational institutions.

1. Psychological-pedagogical mechanisms. Psychological-pedagogical mechanisms can be used in the real practice of a higher education institution only in the conditions that lead to an organic combination of the activity of the environment and the activity of the student's personality in the formation of competitive advantages. In addition, conscious calculations and the use of psychological-pedagogical mechanisms by teachers should be proportionate to the content of the educational object. The formation of a competitive graduate, such as certain qualities and personal qualities that provide him with a competitive advantage, can be realized only in the process of experiences - in the emotional changes that take place in the real life of the student. In addition, the activity of pedagogical and psychological mechanisms of formation of a competitive graduate of a higher educational institution includes a strong system of interrelated events and factors that ensure the success of the formation of competitive characteristics and the characteristics of the student's personality by creating false professional situations.

In the process of solving them, the professional and personal potential of a graduate of a higher educational institution, a future specialist is revealed, the need for professional and personal self-improvement is formed, and the student's self-knowledge and understanding is ensured.

In practice, psychological-pedagogical mechanisms can be implemented in the educational and non-educational activities of students in the following forms: presentation, discussion of educational projects (models) developed by them, and general evaluation of the quality of their implementation; creative developments, organization of student creative team, focus group, professional competitions "The best of the profession", discussions, excursions for successfully developing enterprises of various forms of ownership, etc. In addition, psychological and pedagogical mechanisms may include:

- by pedagogically supporting students' enthusiasm for controlled intellectual activity, to deepen the motivation of mapping prospects in the modern labor market, and by emotionally involving students, to increase the level of appropriate use of their theoretical knowledge and professional experience;

- Pedagogical support of the process of "teaching" students, controlled by thinking activity with changes to goals, value system, cognitive, humanitarian requirements, as well as market culture;

- development of mental education of students by "observing" models of professional behavior of a specialist.

2. Organizational-management mechanisms. A higher education institution with its entire structure or its separate components creates appropriate conditions and opportunities for students, which together help to reveal the student's personal and social capital. In addition, in the process of teaching knowledge, norms and social values by a higher education institution, as defined in the Russian vocational education system, the student is imagined as a subject who collects information about new knowledge, values and his own views. awakens and reacts in response to this learning process. In other words, depending on the organizational work of the higher education institution, the individual achievements of students (including the formation of their competitiveness in the modern labor market) and, as a result, their future professional career are distinguished.

In order to achieve the strategic goal of the pedagogical strategy within the framework of the organizational-management mechanism, the following can be formed:

- a structure coordinating the procedure, actions and activities defined in the strategic plan for the implementation of the pedagogical strategy of forming a graduate of a competitive higher education institution (for example, the Council for the implementation of the pedagogical strategy);

- working groups and thematic commissions to create strategic priorities for the formation of competitive advantages of graduates in the labor market and to develop programs, plans and projects for the implementation of the pedagogical strategy; they would have provided pedagogical monitoring, implementation, and development of the pedagogical strategy of forming a graduate of a competitive higher education institution in selected strategic areas, making changes to strategic instructions;

- Higher education that offers directions that provide a connection between the state, employers (all types of private enterprises), public and strategic cooperation, public-private partnership, social cooperation, and the formation of competitive advantages in original production and graduates. organizational and management mechanism of educational institutions.

3. Scientific-methodical mechanisms are aimed at accelerating the intellectual and creative activity of students aimed at increasing and using new knowledge in order to solve various social, economic and other problems. Undoubted relevance and importance of students' scientific-research activity is that they can go beyond the established norms of higher professional education, and sometimes material-technical and other resources available to higher educational institutions. Due to this, the following can be considered as scientific and methodological mechanisms for implementing the pedagogical strategy of forming the competitiveness of a graduate of a higher educational institution:

- Appropriate scientific support for the process of forming a competitive graduate student by developing the infrastructure of the higher education institution, the scientific potential of the higher education institution's professor-teacher team, etc.;

- Modeling a methodological system for the implementation of a pedagogical strategy in the form of components such as subjects, principles, pedagogical conditions, levels, content and means of evaluating the educational outcome of graduates of a higher educational institution.

4. Socio-economic mechanisms of implementing the pedagogical strategy of forming the competitiveness of the university graduate are an external set of interrelated elements that ensure the disclosure of the student's personal and social capital. Among such mechanisms we can include:

- regular targeted social work with students, taking into account the proven value system of meeting the needs of each student by the higher education institution, supporting talented young people, solving employment issues, housing problems to do, including providing support to young families, young entrepreneurs and others;

- regularly carrying out targeted educational work with students includes the following activities: working with captains and leaders of study groups, working in student residences, monitoring attendance, cultural and sports-health activities with students and others;

- as an integral part of the vocational education program, training students and improving the quality of educational and production practices, designing internships, diplomas, and managing

their activities for students, such as presentations of their potential by graduates at job fairs. creates the ground for the horse.

5. Information-pedagogical mechanisms, the implementation of the pedagogical strategy for the formation of a competitive graduate of a higher educational institution, the formation of professional problem-solving skills, interrelated with the organization of information sources of a specific higher educational institution student guesses. The main list of information-pedagogical mechanisms:

- multimedia development systems;
- use of internet technologies and internet library;
- development of the information site of the higher educational institution, etc.

6. Mechanisms related to personnel for the implementation of the pedagogical strategy of forming a graduate of a competitive higher educational institution - a systematic and conscious unification of the actions of the professor-teacher team to achieve the goals of the higher educational institution. Among such mechanisms we include the following:

- development and implementation of modern personnel management technologies of higher educational institutions;

- to support the valuable instructions of the profession of a teacher of a higher education institution, especially: orientation to independent creative expression through one's profession, striving to regularly improve the quality of teaching, developing a sense of responsibility for one's profession, etc. support and implementation;

- to arouse enthusiasm and a sense of appreciation in the teacher of a higher educational institution for the process of forming a competitive graduate of a higher educational institution.

7. Legal mechanisms include the development of a package of normative legal documents regulating the process of implementing the pedagogical strategy of forming a graduate of a competitive higher education institution, as well as monitoring its implementation during the entire process of forming competitive characteristics and personal qualities of a graduate student.

In the research work, pedagogical conditions for the implementation of integrative mechanisms of pedagogic personnel training in the conditions of social cooperation in the higher educational institution were studied.

Development is a process of regular change from one state to another, more perfect state; is the transition from old to new quality, from simple to complex, from bottom to top. The development process, in addition to integration, is also characterized by the presence of differentiation, which is connected with the separation and division of the developing whole into parts, stages, levels. In the scientific literature, the correlation between leveling and integration is considered in the following several situations: 1) in the interactions that formed the essence of its evolution, as well as the interrelated aspects of the development of matter; 3) opposite sides of a process, which are rarely in harmony, often one of the sides prevails. In the totality of the processes of integration and differentiation, the development of the whole, and its basis - opposition lies.

Integration (Latin integer - complete, whole, intact; complete; integratio - restoration), N.K. According to Chapayeva, systematic education can be divided into several aspects: procedural, final, and also a summative whole. Most researchers define integration, first of all, as a process, as a constant effort to restore and integrate parts of one's whole.

The analysis of views and opinions of different authors made it possible to distinguish several aspects in the understanding of integration in relation to the problem of system development.

First, integration is the reason for the emergence of this system. For example, E. Durkheim considers society as a whole, and as the reason for its emergence, he defines the successive formation of associations, the elements of which are closely connected with each other in one way or another.

Secondly, integration as a product of system development.

Thirdly, integration is a factor of system development, that is, the driving force of its development.

Fourthly, integration is a condition of system formation.

Fifth, integration is to combine the goals and factors of education into a whole. Integration - Latin "integer" - totality, "integerara" - filling, creating, restoring the totality. The problems of ensuring harmonies in the content of education are also a field of integration. It is to teach generalization of concepts.

The need to consider integration together with differentiation is a requirement for a holistic approach to the essence of integration processes. The unity of the processes of integration and differentiation in education is connected with the concept of "intentionality" introduced by V.F. Morgun. Educational intention is a moving transition between integration and differentiation of educational content, education and training methods, educational institutions, which are both the needs and opportunities of society, and the abilities and interests of the individual. depends.

The integration of educational content is defined as the process and result of the interaction of its constituent elements, along with the consistency and increase of students' knowledge.

Integration of the educational process is the process of forming the integrity of the educational process based on the interaction of subjects, the interdependence and mutual absorption of purposeful, meaningful, technological, effective components.

The integrated pedagogical process is a process of interdependence with the teacher's methodical activity and the student's methodical activity in parallel with the main processes (educational activity, cognitive activity).

The main criteria of integration (educational content) V.S. Bezrukova defines as follows: identification of integration goals; selection of objects (sources of integration); determining the system-forming factor of integration; establishing a new structure of the course; content processing; performance testing.

Analysis of studies has shown that integration includes (voluntary) unification of unequal partners differing in size and resources. One of the main mechanisms of integration is fusion (fusion, amalgamation, merger). "Unification" means to unite, form a whole, join together.

In the scientific and pedagogical literature, several concepts are used to define the integration of educational institutions:

- integration in education is the interaction of various types of educational institutions, as well as structural-institutional changes, with enterprises, scientific and cultural institutions, which are manifested in the creation of integrative complexes. form of interaction;

- integration at the level of structural changes in educational institutions - establishing continuity between educational levels and forming a multi-level model of an educational institution;

- structural integration - unification of faculties and research institutes in the same areas of activity and creation of educational and scientific complexes with a single scientific council and management system.

The structural aspect of the unification of educational institutions lies in the design of coordinated training programs at different levels of professional training, in the development of end-to-end training programs for all stages of education, in the unification of the content of different stages of life. In this case, it implies consideration of training programs and plans as an object of integration.

The organizational aspect of the integration of educational institutions envisages their interaction, the creation of voluntary associations, complexes, and the creation of integrated educational institutions.

Factors affecting integration processes in the modern education system can be divided into external and internal. External factors of integration:

the need to fulfill the social order of society to train teachers with high professional competence;

state policy in the field of education;

the processes of integration of educational institutions that often occur in the vocational education system in general;

the influence of other integration processes (especially in recent times - international integration in education).

Internal factors of integration:

the general idea, the generality of the implemented activities, the only goal - to jointly search for effective models of teacher training, to develop him as an indispensable person, professional;

the desire to optimize the structure and activity of educational institutions, to accumulate integral potential;

strive to coordinate the activities of educational institutions for the joint use of resources (material, economic, human, informational, etc.)

as a result of the merger of pedagogical and other educational institutions, a single informational educational space will be created.

Thus, the development of the integration process is influenced by the following groups of factors: political, social, economic, resource, legal, pedagogical, personnel, territorial. In conclusion, it can be said that the training of pedagogues on the basis of social cooperation is a condition for the implementation of the social order, that is, a guarantee of the high quality of the set of knowledge, skills and abilities of the future professional in the field of education.

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